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Investigating the Performance of Mathematics and Technology and Livelihood Education Teachers in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan and Its Implications for Grade 8 Students' Academic Performance

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Abstract

Quality teaching is widely recognized as a crucial factor in enhancing students' academic achievement, particularly in core subjects such as Mathematics and Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE). However, limited studies have examined how the performance of these teachers directly relates to the academic performance of Grade 8 students, especially within the context of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan. This study investigated the performance of Mathematics and TLE teachers in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan and examined its implications for the academic performance of Grade 8 students. Employing a descriptive-comparative research design, data were gathered from 32 Grade 8 Mathematics and TLE teachers across twelve secondary schools offering the Revised Basic Education Curriculum. Teacher profiles included age, sex, position, years in service, and highest degree obtained. Instruments used were a survey questionnaire, RPMS performance ratings, and students' final grades in Mathematics and TLE. Statistical tools, including frequency distribution, mean, standard deviation, chi-square test, t-test, and two-way ANOVA, were applied.

Findings revealed that most teachers were under 30 years old, predominantly female, in Teacher III positions, with 0–3 years of teaching experience, and had earned units in master's degrees. Both Mathematics and TLE teachers achieved very satisfactory performance ratings, with Mathematics teachers slightly outperforming TLE teachers. Age was found to significantly influence the performance of Mathematics teachers, while sex, position, and educational attainment showed no significant effect. Students showed very satisfactory performance in both subjects, with slightly higher achievement in TLE. A moderate, positive correlation was established between teachers' performance ratings and students' academic performance, indicating that higher teacher performance is associated with better student achievements.

The study recommends that teachers complete their master's degrees, strive for outstanding performance ratings, and engage in professional development activities. Further research in other subject areas is also suggested.

Keywords: Mathematics, Technology and Livelihood Education, teacher performance, student academic performance, descriptive-comparative research, correlation

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